

DEVELOPMENT OF PERIODIC COST ACCOUNTING IN BUSINESS ENTITIES IN ACCORDANCE WITH INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS OF FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING

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Abstract: This scientific article explores the development of periodic cost accounting in business entities, with a particular focus on its alignment with international standards of financial accounting. The adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) has significantly impacted the way businesses account for costs and expenses, emphasizing transparency and consistency in financial reporting. This article discusses the evolution of cost accounting, the importance of periodic cost accounting in modern business operations, and the convergence of cost accounting practices with international financial reporting requirements.

Keywords: Periodic Cost Accounting, International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), Cost Allocation, Transparency, Comparability, Consistency, Financial Reporting, Cost Accounting Practices, Capitalization of Costs

Cost accounting is a fundamental component of financial reporting and management within business entities. It involves the process of tracking, recording, and analyzing costs and expenses incurred in the production of goods and services. Over time, the landscape of cost accounting has evolved, and with the globalization of business operations, aligning cost accounting practices with

international standards has become essential. This article explores the development of periodic cost accounting and its harmonization with international financial accounting standards.

Historical Perspective: The history of cost accounting can be traced back to the early 19th century when businesses began recognizing the need to allocate costs to products or services to determine their profitability. Traditional methods such as job costing and process costing were widely used to assign costs to specific products or production processes. However, these methods lacked uniformity and comparability, which became increasingly problematic as businesses expanded internationally. [1.16] **The Emergence of IFRS:** The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), developed by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), have played a pivotal role in shaping modern financial reporting practices. The adoption of IFRS by many countries and multinational corporations has led to a shift in the way costs are accounted for in financial statements. IFRS emphasizes the principles of consistency, comparability, and transparency in financial reporting. The emergence of the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) represents a significant milestone in the field of accounting, ushering in a new era of financial reporting practices that prioritize consistency, comparability, and transparency. Developed by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), IFRS has gained widespread acceptance and adoption by many countries and multinational corporations worldwide. This section delves deeper into the pivotal role played by IFRS in shaping modern financial reporting practices, especially in the realm of cost accounting. [2.86] **Global Adoption of IFRS:** One of the key factors that underscore the importance of IFRS is its global adoption. As businesses expanded their operations internationally, the need for a common set of accounting standards became evident. IFRS emerged as a response to this need, with the aim of harmonizing accounting practices on a global scale. Today, IFRS is recognized and accepted in numerous countries, making it the most widely used accounting framework in the world. **Consistency in Reporting: IFRS**

places a strong emphasis on consistency in financial reporting. This consistency is achieved by establishing clear and uniform accounting principles and practices that apply to various aspects of financial reporting, including cost accounting. Businesses that adhere to IFRS are required to consistently apply these principles across reporting periods, ensuring that financial statements are presented in a manner that facilitates meaningful comparisons over time.

Comparability Across Entities: Another hallmark of IFRS is its focus on comparability. Under IFRS, businesses are encouraged to present their financial information in a manner that allows for meaningful comparisons with other entities in the same industry or sector. This comparability is essential for investors, regulators, and stakeholders who rely on financial statements to make informed decisions. For cost accounting, comparability enables stakeholders to assess how efficiently a company manages its costs relative to its peers.

[3.29] Transparency in Financial Reporting: Transparency is a fundamental principle of IFRS. It requires businesses to provide clear and comprehensive disclosures in their financial statements. In the context of cost accounting, transparency involves disclosing the methods used to allocate costs, the basis for recognizing costs as assets or expenses, and any significant cost-related assumptions. This transparency ensures that users of financial statements have access to the information necessary to understand the cost structure of a business.

Impact on Cost Accounting Practices: The adoption of IFRS has led to a significant shift in how costs are accounted for in financial statements. For instance, IFRS introduces specific requirements for the capitalization of costs related to the production of inventory, aligning the recognition of these costs with revenue recognition principles[4]. This change ensures that costs are matched with the revenue they generate, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of financial reporting. In summary, the emergence and widespread adoption of IFRS have transformed cost accounting practices in business entities. IFRS promotes consistency, comparability, and transparency in financial reporting, which are essential for making informed investment decisions

and assessing a company's financial health. As IFRS continues to evolve, its influence on cost accounting is expected to remain a critical driver of harmonized global accounting standards.

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